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JĪRṆŌDHĀRAṆA KUMBHĀBHIṢEKAM – THE INDIGENOUS METHOD OF CONSERVATION AND PRESERVATION

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Abstract

Jīrṇōdhāraṇa Kumbhābhiṣekam is a culmination of tangible and intangible heritage methods prevailing in the temples of South India. The traditional science behind, the ritualistic purification techniques along with its philosophical aspects are to be understood in order to understand the temple complex. These indigenous methods support the temple structures to survive hundreds of years in their original form and shape. The built heritage along with its cultural continuum beholds the tangible and the intangible culture together. These traditional methods are widely time tested and are philosophical and scientific in nature and are intertwined with the regional culture and society.

Keywords: *Jīrṇōdhāraṇam, Kumbhābhiṣekam, Temple, Indigenous, Traditional science, Conservation.*

Jīrṇōdhāraṇa Kumbhābhiṣekam is the ancient mode of ritualistic purification. It is a culmination of tangible and intangible heritage methods which have been prevailing since more than a millennium on the southern part of the subcontinent. *Jīrṇōdhāraṇam* is the process of cleaning, conserving, restoring, and re-installing techniques used in the temple complex, whereas *kumbhābhiṣekam* is the ritualistic purification and consecration of the newly erected sacred complex. The materials used and the prevailing techniques are thoroughly indigenous, ancient, and scientific in nature. These methods are tested over a prolonged period and have come through generations.

Temple – The Tangible and intangible heritage continuum

Temple is a sacred place built by the manifestation of human physical form into the metaphysical form in relation to the earthly and heavenly bodies. It is a place for worship and belief. The construction and the consecration of the temple is completely based on *Vāstuśāstras, Āgamas, Śilpaśāstras* and *Purāṇās* which possess high cosmic and scientific values. We have more than twenty-five ancient reference books for temple construction. *Kāśyapa, Mayamata, Mānasāra, Viśvakarmiya, Aindra matam, Sarasvatīyam, Brahmiyam, Sagalātikāram, Śilparatna, Marichisamhita* are some of the famous ancient books¹.

Every procedure of temple construction has a ritual process along with its individual and scientific importance. The process of transforming an ordinary place into a sacred complex is generally called as '*Jīrnodhāraṇa aṣṭabandhana mahākumbhābhiṣekam.*'

The relation between astro-archaeology, cosmic energy, astronomy, astrology, *vāstuśāstra*, *bhū-śāstra* are significant in the construction of temple.

Temple is a place where the tangible and intangible heritages confluence. Temple as the built heritage structure stands along with the tradition and the rituals which are followed making it a continuum of both tangible and intangible heritages. Intangible heritages like *Slokas*, *Mantras*, *Vedas*, *Āgamas* and *Śāstras* help to know the ritual process and methods, which in turn act as catalysts to perform the ritual process, consecration, conservation, preservation, and heritage management remedies to the built tangible heritage. From the installation of the idols with its physical and metaphysical properties to its cleaning and conservation techniques, it is performed in a detailed manner which is entirely scientific and relatable to modern conservation techniques.

We have literary evidences and epigraphic records for the ancient conservation methods. *Marichisamhita*, *Śilparatna*, *Mānasāra*, *Kāśyapa*, *Pratimālakṣaṇa* of *Viṣṇudharmōṭṭarapurāṇa*, *Bhaviśya purāṇa*, *Bimba-lakṣaṇa*, *Agnipurāṇa* are some of them. Among these, *Marichisamhita* and *Agnipurāṇa* are the most important sources².

Bimba- sthāpaṇam - Installation of images

The installation of the images in their specific socle in a specific space and place is very important in the construction process of a temple. Once the temple is constructed, based on the dimension of the *mūlavar* or *mūla-bimba*, the images will be enshrined in different places made up of stone, metal, and

wood. *Marichisamhita* and *Agnipurāṇa* gives us different rituals and principles to be followed during the process of installation. *Āgamas* state four different types of installation - *Āvartam*, *Anāvartam*, *Punarāvartam* and *Antarītam*.

Āvartam

Āvartam is the ritual process stated for a newly constructed temple. On the process of installation of images, the rites must follow *bhū-parikṣa*; selection of site to the *Kumbhābhiṣekam*. The rituals must include *hōma*, *pūja*, *yagna*, *abhiṣekam* and *ārādhanā*, as mentioned in *Śilpaśāstras* and *āgamic* texts³.

Anāvartam

Anāvartam is the ritual stated for the renovation and reconstruction of a temple structure and complex, which is damaged due to natural calamities like floods, heavy rains, lightning strike, earthquakes, etc. The main image and the other damaged elements of the temple must be renovated and purified by ritual performances and re-installed in their specified socle as earlier using *aṣṭabandhana*.

Punarāvartam

Punarāvartam means recurrence; the process of regaining original state again. This is commonly known as the '*Jīrṇōdhāraṇa-aṣṭabandhana-mahā-kumbhābhiṣekam*.' It has to be performed every 12 years in every temple complex to maintain the sanctity. *Punarāvartam* includes a series of rites and processes which help to clean, curate, consolidate, conserve, and restore the images and structures at the temple. This concept is still practised widely in South Indian temples.

Antarītam

In the case of unexpected accidents, physical damages of structures, theft and robbery, war, unexpected death inside the shrines and drought, this ritual is stated to be processed in the temples. This is performed mainly to purify and consecrate the sacred complex and its locality to regain the sanctity and sacredness.

Among these four types of *sthāpanam*, first and third are still widely in practice in South Indian temples. To understand the concept of ‘*Jīrnodhārana aṣṭabandhana mahākumbhābhiṣekam*’, one should understand the technical aspects of the *jīrnodhārana*.

***Jīrṇōdhāraṇam* – The indigenous conservation of sacred complex**

Jīrṇōdhāraṇam or *Jīrṇōdhāra* is the concept of arresting the process of decay with cleaning, conservation, preservation, restoration, renovation, and reconstruction of a temple complex. The word *jīrṇa* means the process of getting old or to decay, *uddharaṇa* means lifting or raising up and delivering. Together, it makes *jīrṇōdhāraṇam* which gives two meanings: deliverance of decaying (preservation and conservation) and raising up of the old (restoration). Different parts of the temples have different types of *Jīrṇōdhāraṇam* based on their physical state and properties. If the *mūlavar* of a temple is damaged, it must be repaired with the techniques mentioned in the *āgamas* followed by the ritualistic purification. Stone images must be replaced with the same type of stone images. If the damage is small, it can be repaired with a piece of stone and bonded with *aṣṭabandhana*, *svaṛṇabandhana* (gold), silver or indigenous sugar. Metal images can be soldered with the same type of metal if the damage is small. In case of

great damage, the entire metal image can be moulded and reused with addition of same metal composition to it. If the temple is less than 20 years old, the images should be replaced completely. This can be reconsidered in the case of brick-made temples. The *bhera-sthāpaṇam* should be the same as earlier, in terms of both material and size⁴.

Pratimalakṣaṇa, scientifically states the different reasons for damage and decay of edifices, viz., *dagdha* (burnt), *Jīrṇa* (worn-out), *bhanga* (broken) and *sphutita* (split up). *Agnipurāṇa* provides different types of *jīrṇōdhāraṇam*. Namely, *khaṇḍa-jīrṇōdhāraṇam*, *khaṇḍa-sphutita jīrṇōdhāraṇam*, *sputita jīrṇōdhāraṇam*, *sudhakarma*, *taru-gulma-nirmālikarana*, *navakarma*, *nava-sudha karma*⁵.

Khaṇḍa – Jīrṇōdhāraṇa

Etymologically, *khaṇḍa* denotes dismantled members of architecture and *jīrṇōdhāraṇa* indicates the conservation of decaying structure. *Khaṇḍa-jīrṇōdhāraṇa* means repair and restoration of the dismembered sections of architecture. It is a method to restore the pristine state of the dismantled structure. *Viṣṇudharmottarapurāṇa* mentions different types of bonds and adhesives for the construction and repair work. *Vajralepa* and *bandhana* are the bonds and adhesives used in different purposes for fixing and repairing the structures⁶.

Navakarma

Navakarma is an innovative method for structural renovation and restoration. Generally, it is permissible in a *paramsayika vāstu* (non-religious building). Sometimes, *navakarma* is performed in a temple, where the original historic fabric of the sanctum and the

main idol were not altered. In ancient literature and epigraphs, the word *navakarmika*; one who does innovative work, has been mentioned for an engineer capable of constructing new buildings and giving old structures a new look. *Navakarma* included various categories of work like addition, alteration, and complete renovation⁷.

Khaṇḍa-Sphutita-Navakarma

Khaṇḍa-sphutita-navakarma as a method includes the entire process of cleaning, consolidation, and conservation of an old building. This is a multi-methodological practice of conservation of mutilated structures and buildings having various types of accretions. Apart from cleaning and consolidation, adding new and artistic beauty also falls under the preview of this subject⁸.

Sphutita Navakarma

It is suggested for buildings distorted due to overloading, sinking and sub-soil movement. It is a method used for strengthening the building. It is also used for protecting the structures from ageing problems. This method is applied for repairing the distorted sections of edifices by giving them their original shape⁹.

Nava-Sudha-Karma:

Nava-sudha-karma is a technique of lime coating. In ancient India, there had been a tradition of lime coating on the surface of walls and sculptures. It was in practice because lime-coating and coloration of the religious structures were integral to the entire process of the aestheticizing the shrines. This method is prevalent in South India. In Kailāsanāthar temple at Kanchipuram, there is evidence of smooth lime coating on the walls of cloistered niches

of the *prākara-bhitti*. At Ellora, there are remains of such works. For that purpose, the surface of walls and sculptures were kept rough¹⁰.

Taru–Gulma–Nirmālikaraṇa:

Several texts on *vāstu* suggest various trees that can be planted around sacred structures. In fact, *Vāstuśāstra* forbids planting some of the trees within the precincts of temples and residential buildings, which is an important aspect of bio-aesthetics at the sacred shrines. These texts also mention the method of cleaning microbials and vegetal growth from historic structures named *taru-gulma-nirmālikarana*. The word *taru* means plants, *gulma* means microbials and *nirmālikarana* means removing. Thus, this method was stated for the removal of over grown vegetation, microbials, lichens and moss in and around the sacred complex. It is a part of maintenance system which is prevalent at the sacred centres¹¹.

Aṣṭabandhana

It is a natural adhesive paste which is used as bonding and fixating agent to install the stone images in its specified socle. It is a mixture of eight natural components with medicinal value. The two main purposes of this are to hold the images on their specific socle and to keep them intact from the microorganism growth. The eight components of *aṣṭabandhana* are; Red ochre powder, Wood lac, Resin, Beeswax, Sal resin, Cinnabar, White wax, and pure Butter. These ingredients are mixed in specific ratio and grounded seven times making balls and are kept for a few days. Lastly, they are grounded again by adding butter to make it a warmer paste. This warm paste is applied to fix the images on their pedestal, before it becomes cooler. Once it is applied,

the icon is considered ready for consecration. The life span of *aṣṭabandhana* is twelve years as it loses its adhesiveness. After that, it must be replaced with same component. The mixing ratio of *aṣṭabandhana* as mentioned in *Śilpaśāstra* is,

Red ochre powder – 2 parts

Wood lac – 7 parts

Sal resin – 2¼ parts

Beeswax – ¼ parts

Resin – 1 part

Cinnabar – 2 parts

White wax – 1 part

Pure butter – 4 parts¹²

Apart from this, different types of bonds and adhesives are mentioned in *Śilpaśāstras*, *purāṇās* and *āgamic* texts. *Eka-bandhaṇa*, *tri-bandhaṇa*, *pañca-bandhaṇa*, *Sudha-bandhaṇa*, *svarṇa-bandhaṇa*, *mṛtika-bandhaṇa*, *vajra-bandhaṇa* and *vajralepaṇa* are some of the adhesives and adamantine plasters used for the bonding of the sculptures, filling up the cracks on the icons and walls, creating a protective layer on the surface of the shrines and *vimānās*¹³.

Apart from the *Kumbhābhiṣekam* and *jīrṇōdhāraṇam*, *āgamas* and *śāstras* mention different types of rituals to be performed in daily, monthly and yearly basis. It has its own spiritual and scientific values. *Nityapūja*, *brahmōtsavam*, *kalyāṇa mahōtsavam*, *pakṣa pūja*, special occasions, like *janmadin*, *Śivarātri*, *saṣṭi*, *aṣṭami*, *ekādaṣi*, etc. Some of the rituals which are performed in the temples widely, even today are stated below:

Nityapūja

It is the daily ritual rites performed in a temple. *Āgamas* mention, *pañca-kāla-pūja* daily for temples with *gopuram*. A temple without *gopuram* has to perform *tri-kāla-pūja*. This *pūja* includes *samprokṣanam*, *abhiṣekam*, *arcana*, *ārādhanā*, *ubacāra*, *alankāra* and *naivēdya*. Now Tamil Nadu government has passed an order to perform *nityapūja* twice a day in temples.

Samprokṣanam

It is the process of cleaning and curating the icons and preparing it for the *abhiṣekam* and other daily rituals. It means, sprinkling of sacred water on the icons and the sculptures of the temple.

Abhiṣekam

Abhiṣekam literally means pouring or anointing. It is the purification process by using water with various herbal and natural materials. *Śāstras*, *sūtras* and *āgamas* mention 16 types of *abhiṣekam*. Every material used in the *abhiṣekam* has its own value and reason for the cleansing and purifying the icons and sculptures. Milk, curd, oil, ghee, rice flour, turmeric, sandalwood paste, rosewater, *vibhūti*, *kungumam*, honey, lemon, coconut water, *pañcāmirtam* (milk, curd, butter, cow-urine and honey), different types of fruits, herbs like *tulsi*, *asvaganda*, *atimatura*, *neem*, *asvatta* and *bilva* are used in the *abhiṣekam*.

Pañcāmirta snānam

Pañcāmirtam is the combination of milk, curd, butter, cow-urine and honey. It is made as a mixture and used in the *abhiṣekam*. This process cleanses the deposition and layer formation on the

sculptures. This is a scientific method which has been tested. In the year 2000, 'Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj Vaastu Sangrahalaya' and 'Tata Institute of Fundamental Research' together experimented with this method on an image of 'Tāra' belonging to Bihar. The green patination formed on the image was cleansed by a solution [milk (30ml) + curd (30ml) + honey (5ml) + ghee or purified butter (5ml) + lump sugar powder (5gm)]. The image was cleansed thrice and washed by distilled water. It was noted that the chloride and sulphate were absent and the image was clean after this process¹⁴.

Ālepanam

It is a ritual of applying herbal paste on the images and cleaning it. *Tulsi, elaichi, lavanga, triphala, asvadha, bilva* and camphor are used to make a paste. This paste is applied over the images and cleaned with water.

Scientifically, this cleans the accretions and deposition on the stone images and removes micro-organisms from the joints. This is generally performed in Vaiṣṇava temples.

Sarkarasnānam

It is the method of cleaning images using indigenous sugar or dark sugar. This takes out the oil deposition and gives a glossy and lustrous appeal to the sculptures.

Dadhyōdakam

It is a process of ritual cleaning of images using curd. It is performed both in stone and metal objects. The lactic acid in curd acts as natural detergent which absorbs and cleans the salt and soot deposition.

Gandhōdakam

It is a ritual cleaning with a mixture of *kesara* (saffron), *candana* (cedar) and *haridra* (turmeric). It is high in aromatic and cleansing properties which is considered as highly auspicious.

Each and every material has its own spiritual and scientific values. Curd cleans the oily pigments on the stone surface and salt accretions. Lemon and *vibhūti* together takes the chloride and sulphate layer over the metal objects. *Pañcāmirtam* generally cleanses both the stone sculptures and the metal icons. *Tulsi*, *elaichi*, *lavanga* and edible camphor paste are used to apply over the stone images to take out the oil depositions and the soot deposition. Generally, this is done in *Vaiṣṇava* temples during *tirumañjanam*; a ritualistic purificatory process in *Vaiṣṇava* shrines.

The fruits used in the *abhiṣekam* are rich in citrus content which cleanses the images and give a lustrous appearance. The smoke from the camphor and the *gungulia* (Sal tree resin) cleans the vacuum space of the shrine and avoids the webbing of spiders. The turmeric powder and rice flour are applied and cleaned with curd or milk to remove the soot and oil depositions. The lactic acid content in the milk and curd acts as natural detergent on the icons.

***Kumbhābhiṣekam* - The consecration and ritual purification process of temple**

This is the process of ritual cleaning and purification of a temple along with its sculptures after the construction, conservation, and renovation. It is mentioned as ‘*Kadavul Mangalam*’ and ‘*Perum Santhi*’ in Tamil literatures¹⁵. An inscription of Rajaraja-I mentions the renovation and reconstruction of *śrīvimāna* of

Tirumalavadi and performing *kudamulukku* or *kumbhābhiṣekam* as mentioned on *āgamavidhi*¹⁶. *Kumbhābhiṣekam* must be performed once in every 12 years as per the *Śilpaśāstras* and *Āgama* texts¹⁷. The main reasons are to protect the sacred complex and its elements, maintain the sanctity and to increase their life span.

Apart from these, it is also mandatory to change the *varagu tinai* (Kodo millet - *Paspalum scrobiculatum*) which is filled inside the *stūpi* or *kalaśa* (finial) of temple. This *varagu tinai* acts as lightning arrester for temple. *Stūpi* made of gold, copper or bronze is filled up with *varagu* grain which contains hard, corneous, and persistent husks enclosed over it. The lifetime of this *varagu tinai* is 12 years. So, it becomes inevitable to change it for the safety of temple.

Āgamas mention 64 types of rituals for the installation and consecration of idols¹⁸. The ritual process of *Kumbhābhiṣekam* begins with *bālālayam* and continues till *maṇḍalābhiṣekam*. The *nityapūja* will be performed to the *bālālaya* images. The consecration of *bālālaya* images to the *mūla-bimba* is the process of *kumbhābhiṣekam*. The main concept of this process is to invoke the energy and life from the temporary images to the permanent images at their respective space and place.

Kumbhābhiṣekam as an individual term refers to the ritualistic rites performed during the consecration process of a temple. Rather, as a collective term – *kumbhābhiṣekam* is the renovation, restoration and conservation process undergone at a temple complex. It is the reason the entire ritual and

renovation process is called as “*aṣṭabandhana jīrṇōdhāraṇa mahākumbhābhiṣekam.*” It is still in prevalence in the southern part of the subcontinent.

Kumbhābhiṣekam is the main process of consecration. The energy gathered in the *kumbha* and *kalaśa* at *yāgaśāla* is made a procession around sacred complex through the ambulatory path and then anointed over the images and other sculptures installed in the sacred complex. This process is performed with *Vedapārāyanam* (reciting of Vedas), *pañca-vadya-ārādhana* (five traditional musical instruments), *nātyāñjali* (dance performances) and other ritualistic performances.

The *kalaśābhiṣekam* is performed to all the images installed along with the *vimānās*, *gopuras*, *gopura kalaśa* and the subsidiary shrines. Ritually, it is a purificatory bath for the whole temple complex. Scientifically, it is the cleaning, conserving and rejuvenating process of the temple.

Ritual rites of *Kumbhābhiṣekam*¹⁹

Anujña

It is the process of seeking permission from the God to perform rituals and rites for the temple. This is performed in front of the whole village, represented by *ācārya*, *stapathi*, *arcaka* and *yajamānā* of the temple.

Vignēśvara pūja

Every work in India starts with worshipping Lord Ganapati. It is a *pūja* to worship and pray to Lord *Ganapati* to seek permission and blessings to perform and complete the entire ritual process of the temple.

Dana pūja

Dana-pūja is to worship goddess *Danalakṣmi*; goddess of wealth, to seek blessings to give enough wealth for life and for the process of *Kumbhābhiṣekam*. It also includes the worship of the ritual objects collected for the ritual process. It is performed to denote the sacrifice of entire wealth and objects to God.

Pravesa bali-pūja

It is the worship of the *aṣṭadikpālakas*; guardians of eight cardinal directions, begins with east direction and ends in north-east direction.

Bali-pūja is performed to these *dikpālakas* namely, East – *yakṣa*, Southeast – *rakṣasa*, South – *bhuta*, South west – *pisāsa*, West – *brahmarākṣasa*, North West – *kali*, North – *sarali*, Northeast – *bairavā*²⁰.

Vāstuśanti

It is a process of seeking permission from *vāstupuruṣa*; supernal cosmic man who guards the land. *Brahma* and *vāstupuruṣa* both are worshipped at this time and *bali-pūja* is performed.

Mṛitsangrahana

Mṛitsangrahana is worshipping *bhūmādevi* and collecting the earth (soil) for *angurārpana*. This indicates the importance of land and its prosperity. Ant-hill soil, soil loosened by boar, cow, elephant, oxen, lotus root earth, *kūsa* root soil, soil from the holy rivers, soil from different sacred places are collected and filled in pitchers for the rituals.

Angurārpana

It is a process of vegetating *navadānya*; nine cereals, by filling the collected soil into small pitchers. This denotes prosperity and evolution of life at this individual sacred complex. It is believed, if these sprouts have good growth, the site is pure and possesses good vibration. If, these sprouts do not have good growth, it is presumed the temple construction or the consecration process has some issues. Apart from *navadānya*, *asvatta*, *campaka*, *palasa*, *kadamba*, *arjuna* and mango are also used.

Rakṣābandana

A sacred thread is tied on hands of the ritual specialists to protect themselves from evil thoughts and negativity during the process of *Kumbhābhiṣekam*. It is mainly stated for *ācāryas*, *sthapati*, *yajāmāna*, *śilpi* and *paricārakā*. The thread is adorned with turmeric and tied on the right hand.

Yāgaśāla pravēsam

It is a ritual of constructing temporary *vāstu-yāga-maṇḍapa* to perform *yagna* and *hōma* during *Kumbhābhiṣekam*. Fire altars in different shapes and sizes are installed based on *vāstuśāstra* and *śilpaśāstra*. *Ācārya* and *sthapati* are responsible for designing and executing the *vāstu-yāga-maṇḍapa* with the help of other *sthapatis* and *śilpis*.

The *yagna-vedi* or *yāga-kunda* installed here represents different devatas and *upadevatās* of the *mūla-bimba* of respective temple. The *vedi* is made using unburnt bricks and plastered with clay. Decorations are made in the form of *kōlam*, rangoli, *alpana* and *sarvatōbhadrā* using *kāvi*, rice flour and turmeric powder.

Kumbha sthāpaṇam

This is a process where the *kumbha* and *kalaśa* containing holy-water and various other sacred ingredients are installed in the *yāga-śāla-maṇḍapa*. These *kumbha* can be made of gold, silver, copper, bronze and terracotta. The number of pitchers will be based on the deity it is dedicated to.

Generally, the numbers will be in odd series like 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11. These *kumbha* are decorated using sacred thread, silk cloth, *śri-phala* (coconut with fibre), mango leaves, flowers, sandal paste, turmeric paste, *kunkuma* and *vibhūti*. These *kumbha* and *kalaśa* are filled with sacred water from rivers along with *navaratnas*, gold coins, precious gems, *elaichi*, *lavanga*, *karpūra*, *jayaphala*, *kastūri*, *punugu*, etc., The main *kumbha* will be big and the subsidiary ones will be smaller in size.

A minimum of 1008 *kalaśa*, 1008 *śankha* (conch) and more than 3300 pitchers must be installed at the *yāgaśāla* according to *āgama* and *śilpaśāstra*. A sacred thread (*pavitraka*) is connected from *mūlavar* to the main *kumbha* at the *yāgaśāla*. This thread is made of gold, silver, *dharba* and *kusa* grass. It is believed that the energy gathered in the *kumbha* and *kalaśa* is transferred to the *mūla-bimba* and other images of the complex through this sacred thread. This process is also called *nādisantānam*.

Kalākarṣanam

It is the consecration process for the *kumbha* and *kalaśa* at the *yāgaśāla*. This is a process of *ākaraṣana*, where the energy is gained through the mantra chants and rites performed on the *yagna* at the fire altar of *yāgaśāla*²¹.

Yāgaśāla pūja and hōma

These are the ritualistic rites performed at *yāgaśāla* by *ācāryas* and *aracakās* along with *Śivācāryas* and *Caturvedis* from different places. The *Veda-pārāyana* and *mantra-ārādhanā* will be performed starting with *aṣṭamūrti-pūja*. Different varieties of *prasāda*, fruits, flowers, sweets, honey, herbs, roots, twigs of sacred trees and seeds are given as *bali* in the fire altars²².

Pūrnahuti

Pūrnahuti is the concluding rite performed at the *yāga-śāla*. A fully ripe coconut, *navaratnas*, gold coins, ghee, *navadānyas* and honey are tied up in a silk cloth and placed into to the main fire altar. The *Veda-parāyana*, *pañca-vādyā-ārādhanā*, recitation of mantras and slokas are performed all together to enhance the effect of the final ritual act.

Sparsaguthi

After *pūrnahuti*, the whole energy will be gathered into the *kumbha* and *kalaśa*. These *kumbha* and *kalaśa* are then anointed upon the images and other sculptures including the sacred structures and complex.

Mahābhiṣekam

After the *Kumbhābhiṣekam*, the *pūrnābhiṣekam* is performed. It is to satisfy all the *devatas* and *bhūtagaṇas* who participated in the rites and rituals of the *yagna*.

32 types of materials are mentioned in *āgamas* for the *mahābhiṣekam*²³. *Śōdasa-ubacāra* must be performed to the main deity (*mūlavar*) after *mahābhiṣekam*. Pure water, sesame oil, rice flour, turmeric powder, *tirumañjana* powder, *pañcakavya*,

pañcāmirtam, ghee, milk, curd, honey, sugarcane juice, jackfruit, mango, banana, wood apple, lemon, coconut, boiled rice, gold, rosewater, *vibhūti* and sandal paste are the materials used for the *mahābhiṣekam*.

***Maṅḍala-abhiṣekam*²⁴**

From the day of *Kumbhābhiṣekam*, daily *abhiṣekas*, *pūjas* and *hōmas* must be performed for three *pakṣas*. 48 days is one *mandala*. On the 48th day, *pūrnābhiṣekam* is performed and the *visarjana* of *rakṣabandhana* is done. This brings to an end, the entire *Kumbhābhiṣekam* process.

Ritual specialists or Heritologists

Ritual specialists are the people who plan, execute, and organize the construction and ceremonial process of a temple. *Śilpaśāstras* and epigraphic evidences give us a detailed description of the ritual specialists of a temple²⁵.

Ācārya

He is the scholar and the chief guide for the entire ritual. He is the Guru who oversees the whole process of the *Kumbhābhiṣekam*. *Ācāryas* for the Śaivite temples are called *Śivācārya* and the Vaiṣṇavite temples are called *Bhattācārya*. *Āgamas* prescribe that the *ācārya* has to be minimum 45 years of age, following the daily spiritual purificatory rites and rituals. He should know and practice the Veda *kriyās* and *sandhi* rites²⁶.

Sarvasādhaka

He is the main Brahmin who does the *hōmas* and *pūjas* for the entire ritual process. The rituals at the *pradāna hōma-kunda* (main fire altar) are performed by *sarvasādhaka*. *Sarvasādhaka*

should be married and have children as per *śāstras*²⁷. He should follow the *nitya karmās* and *kriyas* performing *agnihōtra* and *nitya-pūja* regularly.

Arcakā

Arcakās are the officiating priests who perform rituals to the main and subsidiary deities of the temple. Each one of them will be assigned an individual shrine for which they have to perform all the ritual process and daily rites. These *arcakās* will be guided and supervised by *Ācāryas* and *Sarvasādhaka*.

Paricāraka

They are the attenders who render assistance to the officiating priests; *Ācārya*, *Sarvasādhaka* and *Arcakā*. They do all the smaller duties and work like supplying water for *abhiṣekam*, lighting the lamps for *ārti*, *pūja* and *ārādhanā*, etc., at regular intervals to the officiating priests when they perform the rituals.

Sthāpaka

They are the people who assemble and arrange all the ritual materials and objects required for the *pūjas*, *hōmas* and the other ritual acts. These people should possess good knowledge of the placement and arrangement of the sacred complex and the *vāstu-yagna-śāla*.

Śri kāryam atikāri

He is the chief executive officer for the day-to-day management of temple and the entire consecration ceremony. He is elected by the villagers and assigned to look after whole process of the ceremony. His job is to ensure that the ritual process continues and completes without any barrier²⁸.

Sthapati

He is the chief engineer and architect of the temple. His job is to plot, plan and construct the temple structure without any defects as mentioned in *śilpaśāstras*. *Sthapati* should be well versed in *śilpaśāstra*, *āgama* and *vāstuśāstra*. He has the privilege to do the installation and consecration of *mūla-bimba* and perform first *abhiṣekam* after the eye-opening ceremony of the sculpture. He is treated as an equal to *Ācārya* and the *Yajamānā*; ruler of the place.

Śilpi

He is the sculptor and the head of artisans for the temple. He should be well-versed in *śilpaśāstra*, *āgama* and *vāstuśāstra*. He is the person who has the responsibility for making and installation of sculptures during the construction and *Kumbhābhiṣekam* ceremony. His job is to work as per the guidelines of the *Sthapati* following the *śilpaśāstras*. The installation of the images on their specified socles is entirely the *śilpi*'s responsibility and duty.

Conclusion

Kumbhābhiṣekam is not only a spiritual ritual and rite performed in the temple to get good will from God. It is entirely scientific in nature which is meant to clean, conserve, preserve, rejuvenate, consolidate, renovate and reconstruct the structures, images, icons and the carriers of the temple. The tangible heritage of the temple is inherited and managed through this intangible ritual process. Every spiritual act has its own scientific and conservative approach which can be related to the modern heritological conservation methods. In fact, intangible heritage like *Śāstras*, *sūtrās*, *āgamas* and *puranas* are not only for spiritual knowledge,

but also describe the life span of different tangible materials along with their conservation and purification techniques.

In the age of modern chemical conservation techniques, these heritological conservation methods – *jīrṇōdhāraṇam* and *kumbhābhiṣekam* can still be used to preserve, conserve, and restore the ancient structures and sacred complexes thus, demonstrating the importance of the indigenous methods of conservation, preservation, and restoration techniques.

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Kumbhābhiṣekam of Gopura kalaśa. Source: pinterest

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